

Performance and Egg Quality Parameters of Laying Hens Fed Diets Supplemented with Processed Bioash

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of processed bioash on the egg quality parameters of laying hens in a bid to explore the efficacy of bioash as a feed additive. Empty palm bunches were collected and processed. The bioash was included in layer diets at four levels: 0.0 kg (control, T1), 0.10 kg (T2), 0.15 kg (T3), and 0.20 kg (T4) per 100kg of feed, replacing common salt (NaCl) in a Completely randomized design. A 12-week feeding trial was conducted with 240 laying hens divided into four groups of 60 birds each with three replicates per group. Performance and, and egg quality parameters were determined. Percentage shell values of the eggs showed significant improvement in the egg shell content among eggs produced by the ash treated birds. Increasing bioash inclusion level in the layer diet resulted in a significant increase in egg shell thickness especially at the 0.10 (1.41mm) and (1.53mm) 0.15kg/100kg diet supplementation levels ($P < 0.05$). There was progressive increase in the values of albumen height (5.17mm – 8.20mm), yolk height (14.40mm – 16.00mm) and albumen index (0.71 – 1.12mm) with increasing inclusion of the bioash. Laying performance parameters showed a significant improvement in hen day production (80.57% - 85.77%) and egg mass (48.00 – 57.46) when compared to the control. The study concludes that supplementing layer diets with bioash at 0.10kg and 0.15kg per 100kg of feed is optimal for improving productive performance and egg quality.

Keywords: Plant waste ash /Plant ash, Egg-type chickens, mineral supplement, , poultry feed

INTRODUCTION

In most intensive poultry production, supplemental minerals are provided in various forms including salts, limestone, oyster shell, bone meal and a wide variety of other forms (Oso *et al.*, 2011; Okoli *et al.*, 2014). However, most of these inorganic elements are usually not readily bioavailable to the animals mainly due to antagonisms amongst themselves, feed ingredients and other nutrients resulting in reduced absorption (Soetan *et al.*, 2010; Okoli *et al.*, 2014). Studies with some plant wastes ashes like plantain ash (Okoli *et al.*, 2014) and palm kernel shell ash (Ohanaka *et al.*, 2022) has shown potential values of ash as good sources of absorbable mineral additive in the diets of pullets and broilers.

Empty palm bunch wastes are readily available agro residues that have found limited application in south eastern Nigeria. They are discarded as waste material and constitute environmental nuisance at several palm oil processing locations (Isreal and Akpan, 2016). Limited quantities are

used as manure in farms while on combustion, the ash has been used to produce local soaps and as edible ash.

Palm bunch ash like most plant ashes has been shown to contain very high levels of potassium salts (Okonkwo *et al.*, 2018), which are reported to negatively influence feed intake at high inclusion level in the diets of chicken. Production of low potassium palm bunch ash may result in a better mineral supplement that would have better effects on the performance and physiology of layers. This will help to solve the problem of reduced feed intake associated with higher inclusion levels of plant ash in broiler and pullet diets (Nwogu, 2013; Ohanaka, 2016) and the poor oviductal and egg shell development in layers (Nwogu, 2013). These problems have been traced to the high dietary electrolyte balance values of diets supplemented with plant ash due to high levels of potassium, sodium and chlorine in such diets (Ohanaka, 2016; Unamba – Opara *et al.*, 2017). It is therefore believed that the reduction of these minerals in the plant ash processed for livestock feeding will yield better results. The study was undertaken to determine the productive and egg quality performance of laying hens fed diets containing feed-grade processed ash.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Empty palm bunches were collected from an oil mill at Umuagwo, Ohaji Egbema local government area of Imo state. They were sundried, burnt and the ash sieved and particles removed. Thereafter, the ash was mixed liberally with water in a plastic bowl to dissolve it. The mixture was allowed to settle for about two days. Subsequently, the product was sieved through a polythene woven sack, and the liquid allowed to drain out. The undissolved solid product was then sundried for about 6 days and stored in a polyethylene sac until needed for analysis. Mineral composition of the processed palm bunch was done at Precision laboratory, Ibadan, Oyo state. Four experimental layer diets were formulated such that the control diets had no palm bunch ash (PBA) while the other three diets had graded levels of PBA inclusion in the diets at 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20kg/100kg of feed respectively in replacement of common salt. All other ingredients were of equal proportion across the test diets. Two hundred and forty (240) layer birds that were 16 weeks in lay were used for the experiment that lasted for 12 weeks. Weight change, hen day production and egg conversion ratio were determined for productive performance. Egg size, egg height, shell thickness, yolk ucolor, yolk/albumen indices and haugh unit were parameters determined for egg quality. All data collected were analyzed statistically using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and differences between the treatment means were compared using the Duncan’s Multiple Range Test using Statistical package for social Sciences (SPSS) user’s guide, Version 24.00 (SPSS, 2012).

Table 1: Ingredient composition of processed bioash -based diets for layer birds (100kg)

Ingredients	T1	T2	T3	T4
	Control	0.10% PBA	0.15% PBA	0.20% PBA
Maize	44.00	44.00	44.00	44.00
Wheat offal	19.00	19.00	19.00	19.00
Soya bean meal	16.00	16.00	16.00	16.00
Brewers dried grain	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Palm kernel cake	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00

Fish meal	1.60	1.60	1.60	1.60
Limestone	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00
Bone meal	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50
Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Lysine	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Methionine	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Salt	0.25	0.15	0.10	0.05
Ash	-	0.10	0.15	0.20
Total	100	100	100	100
Calculated nutrients				
Crude protein (%)	16.20	16.20	16.20	16.20
Crude fibre (%)	5.70	5.70	5.70	5.70
Metabolisable Energy (ME. Kcal/kg)	2650	2650	2650	2650

Vitamin premix contains the following per kg of feed: Vit A = 5,000,000IU, Vit D3 = 1,000,000IU, Vit E = 1875IU, Vit K = 1255gm, Thiamin (B1) = 0.6255gm, Riboflavin= 1.875gm, Calcium panthothenate = 2.8kg, Nicotinic acid = 5.625gm, Pyridoxin = 0.625gm, Vit B12 = 5gm, folic acid = 0.31gm, Biotin = 0.1gm, Cholin chloride = 150gm, methionine = 75gm. Manganese = 5gm, Iron = 10gm, Copper = 1.5gm, Iodine = 0.5gm, Cobalt = 1.0gm, Selenium = 0.05gm, Antioxidane 50gm, Antimold = 7.5gm, Nigrovin = 10gm, Lysine = 75gm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mineral characteristics of processed bioash

Mineral concentrations in the palm bunch ash are shown in table 2. The major minerals were K (164,300.00mg/kg), Ca (74,700.00mg/kg), P (37,800.00mg/kg) and Mg (41,800.00mg/kg) with Cadmium having the lowest (3.51mg/kg). The result is in agreement with some previous work (Nwogu *et al.*, 2014; Van Ryssen and Ndlovu, 2018; Ohanaka *et al.*, 2022) which reported that K, Ca, Mg and P are the major mineral components in plant ash.

Table 2: Mineral concentrations in the palm bunch ash (mg/kg)

Parameters (mg/kg)	Processed ash
Potassium	37,800
Calcium	74,700
Magnesium	41,800
Potassium	164,300
Sodium	11,800

Manganese	1817.54
Iron	1448.22
Copper	303.17
Zinc	507.92
Cobalt	0.00
Chromium	108.98
Cadmium	3.51
Lead	0.00

Laying performance and egg quality of hens fed processed bioash diets

Tables 3 and 4 show the laying performance and egg quality of the hens fed processed bioash - based diets. Hen day production (HDP) was improved by 4.44 – 11.95% over the control value, while egg shell thickness and haugh index values were also improved. The best laying performance results were obtained at the 0.10 and 0.15kg/100kg dietary supplementation and seemed to have been supported by the dietary electrolyte balance (DEB) values of 389.13 and 401.08 mEq/kg diet. Several commercial exogenous enzymes, probiotic and organic acid preparations are being marketed as additives for the enhancement of laying performance (Ohanaka, 2022) The performance enhancement results recorded with those products are however much lower than the results obtained in this study. For example, Sun and Kim (2019) reported percentage HDP improvement of 96.58 to 99.12% with 0.10% supplementation of a commercial multienzyme complex at the 10th week of lay, indicating a minimal improvement of less than one percent. In another study by Khan *et al.* (2011), lay performance was improved from 73.08% to 80.81, 81.00 and 80.98 in laying hens fed diets supplemented with 2.0g/kg antibiotic, 2.0g/kg multi- enzyme and 0.5g/Kg multi- specie probiotics respectively. The PBA, with its significant HDP and shell quality improvement potential could therefore be commercialized as egg production enhancement feed additive. Results also showed that increasing the PBA supplementation level in the layer diet resulted in a significant increase in egg shell thickness especially at 0.10 and 0.15kg/100kg diet supplementation levels (p<0.05). Again, the concentrations of several macro (Ca, Mg, K, and P) and Micro (Fe, Cu and Zn) minerals were significantly elevated by the PBA inclusion of the layer diets.

Table 3: Laying performance of hens fed PBA supplemented diets

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
Initial weight(g)	1816.67	1940.00	1966.67	1816.67	38.21
Final weight (g)	1700.00	1700.00	1833.33	1733.33	38.84
Weight change (g)	-116.67 ^b	-240.00 ^c	-133.33 ^b	-83.33 ^a	61.11
Feed intake (g)	120.33 ^c	120.67 ^c	130.00 ^a	126.00 ^b	1.22
Hen day production (%)	76.66 ^b	85.57 ^a	85.77 ^a	80.00 ^{ab}	1.41
Egg mass	46.00 ^b	52.67 ^a	57.46 ^a	48.00 ^b	0.85
Egg conversion ratio	2.60 ^a	2.30 ^b	2.53 ^a	2.63 ^a	0.04

Means with different superscripts on the same row are significantly different @ P< 0.05

Table 4: Egg quality characteristics of laying hens fed diets supplemented with PBA

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
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Weekly egg weight (g)	57.24 ^b	54.19 ^c	57.43 ^b	60.62 ^a	0.71
Egg shape index (%)	68.72 ^b	75.75 ^{ab}	78.10 ^a	75.00 ^a	0.56
Egg yolk (%)	24.14 ^d	31.03 ^a	24.22 ^c	26.42 ^b	0.84
Egg albumen (%)	63.79 ^a	58.62 ^d	63.64 ^b	62.26 ^c	0.63
Egg shell (%)	12.07 ^b	10.34 ^d	12.12 ^a	11.32 ^c	0.22
Yolk colour	2.00	1.67	1.00	2.00	0.36
Albumen height (mm)	4.80 ^b	5.17 ^b	7.03 ^a	8.20 ^a	0.48
Yolk height (mm)	14.05 ^b	14.40 ^{ab}	15.50 ^{ab}	16.00 ^a	0.33
Albumen diameter (mm)	7.20 ^b	8.00 ^a	7.07 ^b	7.25 ^b	0.11
Albumen index (mm)	0.67 ^b	0.71 ^b	0.99 ^a	1.12 ^a	0.06
Yolk index (mm)	3.74	3.89	3.87	3.94	0.07

Means with different superscripts on the same row are significantly different (P< 0.05)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study was aimed at utilizing processed ash as a useful mineral source for efficient layers feeding. Palm bunch ash with reduced potassium and sodium was produced. The inclusion of layer diet with processed ash is recommended at the inclusion levels of 0.1 and 0.15kg /100kg diet, based on their ability to elicit improved hen day production. and egg quality.

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